

Supplementary material of the article “Cross-validation of 20 anthropometric prediction equations for appendicular muscle mass in older Brazilian women: a cross-sectional study”.

Supplementary Table 1. Proposed anthropometric equations in literature to Predict Appendicular Muscle Mass (AMM) referenced in the Dual-energy X-ray Absorptiometry (DXA) measure with accuracy data (coefficient of determination [r^2] and standard error of estimate [SEE]) of original proposals.

Authors	Sample	AMM predictive Equation (kg)	Adjusted r^2	SEE (kg)
Gomes et al., 2013 ¹⁰	Brazil (n=106; >80 years)	E1 = (0.074×Stature _[cm]) + (0.277×Body mass _[kg]) – (0.144×Triceps skinfold _[mm]) – (0.103×Waist circumference _[cm]) – 0.966 E2 = (0.138×Stature _[cm]) + (0.103×Body mass _[kg]) – 12.489	0.82 0.75	1.67 1.94
Pereira et al., 2013 ⁹	Brazil (n=60 women; 60 to 89 years)	E2 = 4.150 + (0.251×Body mass _[kg]) + (0.011×Forearm circumference _[cm]) – (0.411×BMI _[kg/m²]) E3 = 4.087 + (0.255×Body mass _[kg]) + (0.011×Forearm circumference _[cm]) – (0.371×BMI _[kg/m²]) – (0.035×Thigh skinfold _[mm]) E6 = 2.855 + (0.298×Body mass _[kg]) + (0.019×Age _[years]) + (0.400×Forearm circumference _[cm]) – (0.082×Hip circumference _[cm]) – (0.332×BMI _[kg/m²])	0.73 0.77 0.75	1.21 1.14 1.17
Baumgartner et al., 1998 ⁶	USA (n=149; 73.6±5.8 years)	E1 = 5.8828 + (0.2487×Body mass _[kg]) + (0.0483×Stature _[cm]) + (0.0732×Handgrip strength _[kg]) + (2.5843×Sex _[♂=1; ♀=0]) – (0.1584×Hip circumference _[cm])	0.91	1.58
Santos et al., 2019 ¹⁴	USA NHANES (n=15,239; ≥ 18 years)	E1 = (0.768×Calf circumference _[cm]) + (Ethnicity _[White=0; African American=2.203; Mexican American=-0.540; Other=-0.402]) – (0.029×Age _[years]) – 10.427	0.88	-
		E2 = (0.435×Calf circumference _[cm]) + (0.261×Arm circumference _[cm]) + (0.069×Thigh circumference) + (Ethnicity _[White=0; African American=1.776; Mexican American=-0.965; Other=-0.641]) – (0.035×Age _[years]) – 9.241	0.90	-
		E3 = (0.467×Calf circumference _[cm]) + (0.358×Arm circumference _[cm]) + (0.111×Thigh circumference _[cm]) + (Ethnicity _[White=0; African American=1.730; Mexican American=-0.718; Other=-0.524]) – (0.155×BMI _[kg/m²]) – (0.026×Age _[years]) – 11.886	0.90	-
		E4 = (0.459×Calf circumference _[cm]) + (0.318×Arm circumference _[cm]) + (0.114×Thigh circumference _[cm]) + (0.067×Waist circumference _[cm]) + (Ethnicity _[White=0; African American=1.932; Mexican American=-0.662; Other=-0.416]) – (0.267×BMI _[kg/m²]) – (0.037×Age _[years]) – 13.119	0.90	-
Kulkarni et al., 2013 ¹¹	India (n=799 women; 18 to 79 years)	E1 = (0.170×Body mass _[kg]) + (0.102×Stature _[cm]) – (0.028×Age _[years]) – 9.852	0.82	1.05
		E2 = (0.244×Body mass _[kg]) + (0.082×Stature _[cm]) + (0.087×Calf circumference _[cm]) – (0.058×Arm circumference _[cm]) – (0.102×Hip circumference _[cm]) – (0.023×Age _[years]) – 2.658	0.84	1.01
		E3 = (0.142×Body mass _[kg]) + (0.109×Stature _[cm]) + (0.051×CAMA _[cm]) – (0.027×Age _[years]) – 10.818	0.83	1.02
		E4 = 1.609 + (0.250×Body mass _[kg]) + (0.070×Stature _[cm]) + (0.098×Calf circumference _[cm]) + (0.027×Arm circumference _[cm]) – (0.085×Hip circumference _[cm]) – (1.821×LOG of sum of 4 skinfolds _[mm]) – (0.02×Age _[years])	0.86	0.94
Visvanathan et al., 2012 ⁸	Australia (n=188; 18 to 83 years)	E1 = 9.11472 + 0.36992(Body mass _[kg]) + 5.00840 (if male) – (0.67551×BMI _[kg/m²])	0.90	1.89
		E2 = (0.129727×Body mass _[kg]) + (22.122674×Stature _[cm]) + (4.980820×Sex _[♂=1; ♀=0]) – 27.879919	0.90	1.93
		E3 = 10.047427 + (0.353307×Body mass _[kg]) + (5.096201×Sex _[♂=1; ♀=0]) – (0.621112×BMI _[kg/m²]) – (0.022741×Age _[years])	0.91	1.87
Lera et al., 2014 (only women model) ¹²	Chile (n=308; 69.9±5.2 years)	E1 = (0.107×Body mass _[kg]) + (0.251×Knee height _[cm]) + (0.197×Calf circumference _[cm]) + (0.047×Handgrip strength _[kg]) – (0.034×Hip circumference _[cm]) – (0.020×Age _[years]) – 7.646	0.89 [‡]	1.35
Tanko et al., 2002 ⁷	Denmark (n=754 women; 18 to 85 years)	E1 = (0.11×Body mass _[kg]) + (16.1×Stature _[cm]) – (0.05×Age _[years]) – 13.3	0.58 [‡]	1.70
Ramirez et al., 2015 ¹³	Mexico (n=171; 60 to 86 years)	E1 = (0.215×Calf circumference _[cm]) + (0.112×Stature _[cm]) + (0.093×Handgrip strength _[kg]) + (0.061×Body mass _[kg]) + (3.637×Sex _[♂=1; ♀=0]) – 16.449	0.92 [‡]	1.25

Note: E=equation; BMI=body mass index; CAMA=corrected arm muscle area; LOG=logarithm; [†]=at biceps, triceps, and subscapular and suprailiac regions; * =only white Ethnicity was adopted in the present study; [‡]=not adjusted, NHANES=National Health and Nutrition Examination Survey.

Supplementary Table 2. Descriptive statistics.

Variables	M	95%CI (LL to UL)		SD	Minimum	Maximum	Range
Age, years	69.84	68.41	71.27	5.95	60.00	85.00	25.00
Body mass, kg	66.76	64.01	69.51	11.46	39.35	103.55	64.20
Stature, cm	156.19	154.76	157.62	5.95	145.00	174.00	29.00
BMI, kg/m ²	27.35	26.30	28.41	4.40	18.33	39.95	21.61
<i>Circumferences, cm</i>							
Arm	29.91	29.01	30.82	3.75	22.00	40.80	18.80
Forearm	23.82	23.28	24.36	2.25	19.00	30.00	11.00
Medial calf	34.87	34.16	35.58	2.95	25.20	42.00	16.80
Waist	86.20	83.79	88.61	10.03	65.00	113.00	48.00
Hip	100.63	98.46	102.80	9.04	81.50	128.00	46.50
<i>Skinfold thickness, mm</i>							
Biceps	15.25	13.96	16.53	5.35	5.00	34.00	29.00
Triceps	25.84	24.18	27.50	6.93	9.00	46.00	37.00
Subscapular	28.33	26.23	30.44	8.77	8.00	47.00	39.00
Suprailiac	29.30	27.40	31.21	7.94	8.00	50.00	42.00
Thigh (midline)	32.20	29.57	34.84	10.96	9.00	65.00	56.00
LOG of the sum of 4 skinfolds*	1.98	1.95	2.01	0.13	1.48	2.23	0.76
<i>Segment lengths, cm</i>							
Knee height	49.59	49.08	50.10	2.11	45.00	54.40	9.40
CAMA, cm ²	31.81	29.63	33.99	9.09	17.28	56.93	39.65
Handgrip strength, kg	24.06	22.99	25.12	4.43	12.00	33.00	21.00
AMMDXA, kg	14.57	13.96	15.19	2.56	9.21	22.48	13.27
Predicted AMM, kg							
E1 Gomes et al. (2013)	16.48	15.97	17.00	2.15	11.66	22.81	11.15
E2 Gomes et al. (2013)	15.94	15.54	16.34	1.67	11.78	20.80	9.02
E2 Pereira et al. (2013)	15.96	15.38	16.54	2.42	10.46	24.21	13.75
E3 Pereira et al. (2013)	16.13	15.53	16.74	2.51	10.38	24.10	13.72
E6 Pereira et al. (2013)	16.27	15.70	16.84	2.37	10.86	24.72	13.86
E1 Baumgartner et al. (1998)	15.85	15.35	16.36	2.10	11.30	23.51	12.21
E1 Santos et al. (2019)	14.33	13.77	14.88	2.31	6.75	20.00	13.25
E2 Santos et al. (2019)	14.94	14.33	15.54	2.51	8.77	21.37	12.60
E3 Santos et al. 2020	14.91	14.29	15.54	2.60	8.51	20.98	12.47
E4 Santos et al. 2020	14.31	13.70	14.92	2.53	7.43	20.02	12.59
E1 Kulkarni et al. (2013)	15.47	14.92	16.03	2.30	9.65	22.64	12.99
E2 Kulkarni et al. (2013)	15.87	15.29	16.44	2.39	10.23	23.89	13.66
E3 Kulkarni et al. (2014)	15.42	14.86	15.99	2.35	9.57	22.90	13.33
E4 Kulkarni et al. (2014)	19.91	19.27	20.54	2.63	13.60	28.86	15.26
E1 Visvanathan et al. (2012)	15.33	14.84	15.83	2.06	11.29	21.40	10.11
E2 Visvanathan et al. (2012)	15.33	14.78	15.89	2.32	9.63	21.82	12.19
E3 Visvanathan et al. (2012)	15.06	14.56	15.55	2.06	10.83	21.23	10.40
E1 Lera et al. (2014)	15.13	14.67	15.58	1.90	10.54	20.39	9.84
E1 Tanko et al. (2002)	15.70	15.23	16.17	1.96	10.82	21.23	10.42
E1 Ramirez et al. (2015)	14.85	14.42	15.28	1.80	10.67	19.53	8.86

Note: M=mean; CI=confidence interval; LL=lower limit; UL=upper limit; SD=standard deviation; BMI=body mass index; LOG=logarithm; *=at biceps, triceps, and subscapular and suprailiac regions (in mm); CAMA=corrected arm muscle area; AMM=appendicular skeletal mass; AMMDXA=appendicular skeletal mass measured by Dual-energy X-ray Absorptiometry; E=equation.

Supplementary Figure 1. Agreement between appendicular muscle mass (AMM) predicted with anthropometric equation (E) number 4 of Santos et al. (2019) and AMM measured by Dual-energy X-ray Absorptiometry (AMMDXA).

